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PERSPECTIVISATION OF, AND LOCAL COLOURS, IN *ESIBI* PERFORMANCE

OF AKURE KINGDOM, SOUTHWESTERN, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines *Esibi*, a folk performance of Akure Kingdom, exploring its role in entertainment, activism, socialisation, education, propaganda, and social mobilisation. Using John Dewey's Social Activism Theory, the research analyses the performance's local colours including banters, invectives, call and response, costumes, percussions, praise poetry, and lampoon. The study finds that *Esibi* is an agency of entertainment, activism, and socialisation, promoting gender integration and inclusivity. The study reveals that *Esibi's* local colours are intricate to the performance, making it a unique cultural expression. Through first-hand observations, oral interviews, and direct participation, the research gathered data, which was critically scrutinised through the lens of Social Activism Theory. The theory's emphasis on activism as a tool for ethno-nationalism and social re-engineering made it suitable for the study. The findings highlight *Esibi's* significance in promoting cultural values and social cohesion. The study recommends perpetuating *Esibi* through digital media for wider reach, value re-orientation, and re-perspectivisation. By exploring *Esibi's* role in Akure Kingdom, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the performance's cultural significance and its potential for social impact.

Keywords: Perspectivisation, *Esibi*, local colours, social activism theory, folk-performance

Word count: 250

Introduction

Perspectivisation, also synonymous with perspectivation, refers to the process of assigning a specific viewpoint, standpoint or perspective to a narrative, an event, scenario or description of an aesthetic object through the instrumentality of language. It involves how a speaker, narrator, griot, indigenous performer or writer (re)present information, shaping the reader's or listener's understanding of the situation. This concept is crucial to the understanding of codification and how meaning is constructed in communication, colloquial utterances or quotidian conversation. Its study is not limited to literature, creative writing and folklore alone as it is studied in various fields of human learning and knowledge such as discourse analysis, linguistics, and social psychology. It is the appropriation or assignment of a viewpoint to an experience. Perspectivisation is particularly about choosing a particular "lens", binoculars, angle, standpoint or point of view through which to present information or narrative. This is where the concept is useful to narratives, narratology in literary or folkloric studies. Perspectivisation is informed by individualistic perception of an object or human experience which can be reproduced in various patterns, manners or tenors depending on the individual's descriptive ability and the enrichment of the individual's lexicon. This study attempts the perspectivisation of the local colours in relation to human follies and corrections as predominantly done in the sarcastic tone in Esibi performance among the Akure folks of Ondo State, Southwestern Nigeria.

Akure is one of the major cities in the heart of Yorubaland reputed for the discovery of the heritage or site of a monument known as Iwo Eleeru (the hole or cave of ashes). Akure dialect is an offshoot of the Yoruboid generic language which, according to John Greenberg, belongs to the Kwa Linguistic Group. Akure is the capital city of the present Ondo State, Southwestern Nigeria.

The earliest settlers of Akure were said to have migrated in a hectic peregrination from Ile-Ife, the cradle of Yoruba nationality under the leadership of an Ife prince, warrior and hunter, Asodeboyede. The fathering of the city was said to have dated back to the period around 1150AD, according to the oral tradition of the Akure folks still being propagated in the palace of the Deji of Akure Kingdom. This claim is corroborated by S. Ola Ajimisan in his poem "Akure Ooye" published in *The Archives* (2025) and the vast array of mural paintings or designs on the walls of the Deji of Akure Kingdom's Palace. The poetic accentuation of the history of Akure is extracted from Ajimisan's poem as shown below:

Asodeboyede left the source

In search for what was sauce

For both geese and ganders

His was a no mean journey

His was a hectic sojourn

On the paths crooked and thorny.

At the behest of the oracle

He spread his hegemonic tentacles

Before building blossoming tabernacles

To get his assailants tackled

Until a heated wrestling match
Of ride-or-die ripened into
The breaking of the strings of corals
Slung like the teeth of a cobra... (65)

As waves of expansion intensified, other folks of Edo-Benin ascendancy came to settle there through Oke-Aro, Arakale, Adofure and other entrepots. The city-state derived its name from the breaking of a string of coral beads sequel to intense wrestling between two historical actors as shown in the last lines of the extract above. The totemic animal of the Akure is the African leopard "ekun", which explains why they are praised as "Akure Olooyemekun". This also finds corroboration in the song of the legendary Akure maestro, Wale Glorious, in his albums "Awa l'Akure Olooyemekun" (1960) & "Olootu Awe" (1970). *Esibi* is an interestingly educative Yorubamorphic folklore that is peculiar to the people of Akure. It is, in fact, the Akure-morphic domestication of what is now known as spoken words. Like the Biripo of the Apoi, Ikale and Ilaje of the southern belt of Ondo State, *Esibi* is a multifaceted indigenous performance reputed, treasured and valued by the people of Akure due to its multidimensional outlook and functional indices. It is educative, edifying, satirises social imbalances or socially and morally untoward behaviours among the people. It is as old as the people who practise it.

Meaning and Origin of *Esibi*

Esibi or *Sibi* is an indigenous performance or oral poetry in spoken or chanting mode of amplification and accentuation. While some people see it as just a dance performance, its aesthetical features and stylistic nuances are revelatory of its all-encompassing and fluid tapestry.

Fluidity and flexibility make it more like the ubiquitous bride of Akure sub-nationality of the generic Yoruba family. Generically, it can still be granted ingress into family of ballads. It could be presented in singing mode as well to make its classification into the domain of folk-music or folksong acceptable.

Etymologically, the word Esibi is a morphological coinage derived from two words namely "Esi" which means feedback or response; and "bi" which literally connotes to bear, to birth or result from as a corollary. The word Esibi is a semantic reference to a satirical response which is a corollary of an earlier or initial cynical comment from the lead-poet or performer echoed monotonously or accentuated with slight modifications by the chorus or members of the Esibi troupe known as "Om'Esibi" in the Akure dialect. Esibi, therefore, means the response produced from the comments of a lead performer mimicked by the troupe members who respond like members of a mass choir or large orchestra performing characteristically without sound systems. It is a form of the indigenous poetry of the Akure folks which constitutes a major aspect of their folkism, popular culture or folk-life. It shares a lot in common with the comedy of manners and errors the performance avails the performers the opportunity of using the performance to ridicule, lampoon and correct vogue social vices and misdemeanours across class and status without fear, favour or pretence.

According to Alex Adeoye (2025), the origin of the performance is traced to Oba-Ile during the reign of Oba Obagbeyi. This is captured below:

The onisibis are in full action during this particular festival that
has its origin in Oba-Ile (a part of Akure kingdom).

The traditionalists dance around the town in seven days
as a form of rites to appease the gods for peace in the town.

The Onisibi dancers which are either male or female are always
half-dressed (females are seen in wrappers tied up
to their chest while the males only wear big skirts and are both adorned
with beads and cowries). At the end of the festival, they share drinks
with the town's monarch, the Deji of Akure as well as performing other
rites in the king's palace.

Oluwasomi Ajayi (2025) traces the origin of *Esibi* back to the reign of Oba Obagbeyi. His submission is captured below:

it was originally an Oba-Ile festival, but was brought to Akure
through Deji Obagbeyi (1313) who was a Prince in both Akure
and Oba He was used to this festival when he was in Oba.

When the Oracle picked him to become a king in his father's land,
Akure, he requested that the festival be extend to Akure

Like the typical and epistemic logic in Yoruba culture, which says "oro p'esi je" meaning the matter on ground has also birthed an appropriate response, *Esibi* derived its name from colloquial utterances or quotidian conversation which is believed to be rhetorical. Therefore, *Esibi is a*

product of indigenous rhetorics and native intelligence lexically calibrated to accommodate all forms of contexts and occasions whether formal or standoffish. *Esibi* performance is a performance that thrives on word-game and response which can better be seen as satirical or sarcastic utterances that come with ready-made responses.

Its nuance-bank is characterised by semantic elasticity and elasticity of contextuality or intertextuality in that it can be adapted or tweaked to suit any context. *Esibi* performance can be staged and performed to the accompaniment of indigenous percussions with dramatization; which gives justification to the situation of the performance within the ambits of theatre as well as poetic form. The liminal folkloric, aesthetic and performative elements in the performance include banter, sarcasm, invectives, proverbs, panegyrics, praise poetry, saws, idioms, innumerable pastoral and homiletic nuances that make the performance flexible and adaptable to any ceremonial context. According to the functionalist theorists, the perpetuation of the performance finds justification in the various networks of needs to which it ministers. Explored through the theoretical binoculars of Richard Schechner's Performance Theory, the performance can be put up on the paths, streets, open space and any setting available or be subjected to scenic improvisations. The performance is characterised by fluidity with every social status, class, gender and even royalty and aristocracy. During the field works, especially on August 12, 2025; one of the performances staged at the main auditorium of the Deji of Akure Kingdom's Palace called "Ua Lila" which means the large courtyard, the lead performer was heard creatively throwing banter at the Deji in his presence. He did same to one of the leading title holders, one of the closest allies of Kabiyesi, Chief Asamo. According to Olusola Owolanke (2025),

The origin of the performance is immemorial. It dated back to the

pre-literate era or periods before the advent of western civilisation and literature. In the early days of the existence of the Akure folks, when there were no theatre buildings built for the entertainment of the folks, when there were no schools, churches or literary texts for teaching moral or providing entertainment socialisation and social cohesion except *Esibi* performance. The performers or troupe members, usually members of the same age grade used to gather under the shade of trees after the hectic day's work to regale the agrarian community of Akure with *Esibi* performance.

Oluwasomi Ajayi (2025); Adesola Ajimisan (2025) and Alex Adeoye (2025) lend credence to the claims above. They believe that *Esibi* is an aspect of the folk-life and popular culture of the people Akure which had undergone stages of evolutionary transfiguration occasioned by the influxes of foreign culture. Adesola Ajimisan is of the opinion that the date of origin of *Esibi* is usually unknown and no one can lay claim to its authorship. This claim of Ajimisan above about communal or collective authorship justifies and validates the inclusion of *Esibi* to the catalogue of Yoruba-morphic oral poetry or indigenous performance.

As time went on and as there was expansion, minstrelsy became a child of necessity in *Esibi* artistry. *Esibi* performers began to move from door to door in search of patronage. Thus, what initially began as a ritual accompaniment or satirical tool, confined to under the shade became like

a travelling theatre or mobile orchestra for making money and a source of revenue generation for the troupe members. Adesegun Adedipe (2025) is of the opinion that "from confinement of *Esibi* to the palace courtyard or tree shades, *Esibi* transfigured to a denizen of the streets, village footpaths, marketplaces and even farm-huts". This new development makes the dissection of the performance through the theoretical binoculars of Richard Schechner's Performance Theory possible and exceedingly interesting. Overtime, learning the artistry which is called apprenticeship became entrenched and enshrined through observational learning or imitative inculcation. Members learn from the lead performers and younger members of the society were gradually integrated and inducted into the school of *Esibi* learners, though without specified period of pupillage or learning duration.

Like other oral poetry or indigenous performances, *Esibi* had gone through turbulent transformative stages to survive the renaissance of modernity, westernisation and infiltration of imported cultures by which the digital age is characterised. It suffices to say that it has eternally stood the test of time and the jackhammer of multiculturalism and multilingualism for which the global history of human progress and innovation is reputed. Perspectivisation of the gender space in the performance is as interesting as the aesthetics in it.

Esibi performance is also characterised by gender inclusivity or gender-consciousness in that there is no gender barrier to membership of the troupe. It is possible to have an all-male, all-female or mixed-gendered troupe. In modern age especially through the instrumentality of the digital media, Oluwaseun Oshodi is blazing the trail in *Esibi* artistry. This gender parity or equality in *Esibi* performance is also a replication of the respect for both genders in Akure culture; microcosm of the macrocosm of Akure customary practice of placing tremendous value on the

position of the "Are-mo-binrin" in their monarchy and every family. In the palace of the paramount ruler of Akure (Deji), there is a separate pathway called "Ona Obinrin" which is exclusively for females and males are forbidden from entering or exiting through it. The pathway was created by the earliest designers or Akure indigenous architects with peculiarities of the feminine gender in mind. At the emergence and enthronement rite of passage of a new Deji when he ascends Orioke-Omolore which is adjacent the main entrance of the palace, it is with his eldest female child who automatically becomes the regent of the kingdom on the passing of her father. The performance is preponderantly characterised by the preponderance of extemporaneous call or delivery and spontaneous responses.

In troupe formation, there is no limit in the population of the troupe because the more members of the troupe, the merrier and compelling the performance. The gender-consciousness in the performance is an embodiment of Akure folklore as entrenching and embodying mutual respect for and collective synergy of both genders in the consummation of a successful performance and living a successful communal life. With *Esibi*, communalism or collectivism subsists not only in the walk of the people but also in their quotidian talk. Therefore, population density is an added advantage for the troupe in the areas of modulation and synchronisation, since they usually do not make use of sound systems during most of the performances.

Child enlistment into the troupe is also worth mentioning. Armed with the belief that the cult into which young members are not initiated will go into extinction, young members are enlisted into the troupe yearly, to ensure continuity. This account for the reason there are children among the troupe. They are the proteges or disciples who graduate, with time, into adult troupe members who carry on the legacy and are seen as the future apologists, faces of the performance

and certificates of its survival through ages. Moyo Eso (2025) outlines some intricate aesthetic features of *Esibi* as succinctly revealed below:

In Akure dialect, the lead performer called Onisibi is known as a traditional dancer or troupe of traditional dancers. Like the *Biripo* of of the Ilaje, Ikale and Apoi of the southern belt of Ondo State, *Esibi* is actually more than a dance as it incorporates other nuances from the traditionalists. Their style of music is known as ‘Sibi’.

The performers or traditionalists are therefore called ‘Onisibi’.

The sibi dance always take place during one of the major festivals in the town called ‘Aheregbe’ festival during which people are forbidden from opening shops or display their wares because they will be looted as traditional sanction.

The onisibis are in full action during this particular festival that has its origin in Oba-Ile (a part of Akure kingdom) (26).

Adesola Ajimisan (2025) extends the context of the performance of *Esibi* to ritual as she affirms that the performance transcends just entertainment and cultural socialisation. She maintains that the performance of *Esibi*, which has now metamorphosed into secular entertainment, has a nexus with Aheregbe Festival. In her opinion, it is the preparatory indigenous feast of fraternisation or

re-union that predates either Aheregbe or any of the major festivals in Akure. She goes further to add that

The dancers/performers, who are mostly traditionalists dance around the town for seven days as a form of rites to appease the gods for peace in the town. The Onisibi dancers which are either male or female are always half-dressed (females are seen in wrappers tied up to their chest while the males only wear big skirts and are both adorned with beads and cowries). At the end of the festival, they share drinks with the town's monarch, the Deji of Akure as well as performing other rites in the king's palace.

Damilola Ogunlana (2025) lends credence to the postulation of Adesola Ajimisan above. He said although he is not from the city of Akure. It is the Akure dialect that is spoken in his own part of the territory carved into Akure North Local Government Area. He affirms that the performance, like other medieval or Greek festivals, is an offshoot of the ritual life of the people who have institutionalised it as a preparatory liturgy in Aheregbe Festival before it became deradicalized and transplanted onto the entertainment landscape of the people's history. This evolutionary transfiguration of the performance from ritual to feast or entertainment is in tandem with the postulation of Richard Schechner (1995) in *The Future of Rituals*. Schechner contends that what

is conserved to the sacred groves, temples, traditional arena or square can also pass for entertainment if dismembered from its original abode, the sacred territory. Ayo Kunle (2025) registers his opinion on the origin of Aheregbe Festival and *Esibi* in the succinct explanation below:

The Aeregbe festival originated during the reign of an Oloba of Oba-Ile. A prince, having erred, was rebuked by his father, which led to the prince's decision to leave for the farm in anger. Unfortunately, he accidentally left a fire burning in his hut (Aere), which caught fire and resulted in his death. Upon hearing the news, the Oloba lamented, "Aere un gbe niyen," from which the festival's name, Aeregbe, is derived. To immortalise the prince's memory, the Oloba instituted the Aeregbe festival, which includes traditions such as frying bean "Akara Kengbe" (Akara Aeregbe) and closing markets and stalls in honour of Oloba prince. Five days after the festival, the Oloba sends 45 Akara Obagbeyi (bean cakes) to the Deji of Akure through emissaries, a practice that dated back to when Obagbeyi left Oba-Ile to become Deji. Later that day, the *Esibi* dancers

perform at Igbo Oluoroke in Oba-Ile before proceeding to the Oloba's palace, where they are treated to 45 akara and 25 pekere (maize-baked snack). Furthermore, five days after this event, the Deji will send Eran (goat) Iruna to the Oloba. Historically, this tradition involved sending a human stranger, but it has since been replaced with a goat.

Schechner (1988), in *Performance Theory*, observes that the possible dismemberment of any sacred activity from the sacred temples, creatively tweaked, can pass for entertainment and merry making in customary ceremony, stripped of its taboos and sacred, inviolable myths. Sequel to the nexus of the performance with Aheregbe Festival (a fusion of spirituality with secularism), the Asoga is the chief officiant and the physical head of the spiritual echelon, while Oloundan is the leader of the performers of *Esibi*. Oloundan means the one with weird or esoteric voice believed to be guttural enough to invoke the deities of the land into festive fraternisation with the living and transpose the living into the realm of the ancestors. He and the Asoga are key physical actors in the drama featuring and impersonating the living and ancestral spirits of the land. The current Oloundan is Oluwaseun Oshodi. Both the Asoga and Oloundan mediate between two spaces of the seen and the transcendental, unseen spaces. This duality makes *Esibi* performance unique and esoterically mesmeric. This change of voice is allegorical. It is symbolic of the transfiguration from ordinary beings to both human and spiritual beings. This transformation of voice is an embodiment of spiritual transfiguration into both physical and metaphysical space. It is symbolic of the emplacement of the Oloundan onto the elusive realm of the ancestors who send warning

messages to their living descendants through him (Oloundan). Whether the performance of *Esibi* takes place in the open courtyard, grove, village footpaths, marketplaces or open space, its justification that the performance exemplifies the employment of space as both theatre and stage; and the performance can assume the status of both entertaining non-sacred performance and ritual drama of transition/progression from one phase of collective existence to another suffices.

Theoretical Framework and Methodology

In line with Social Activism Theory, propounded by John Dewey (1916; 1938 & 1987), social activism subsists in conscious actions and sanctions orchestrated by active actors in the society who, through their social and moral consciousness, see to the social sanctification of their society of origin or where they live. Dewey posits that activism constitutes one of the processes through which the society teaches and learns from itself through the agency of various structures and super-structures. Social activism is, thus, hinged on the process of social healing, teaching, re-teaching, learning, re-learning and unlearning of the emergent social realities in the society through conscious activities of virile social actors in order to engender social and cultural rebirth, re-engineering and the renaissance of a new order. Well-thought-out social activism also provokes ethno-nationalism and socio-cultural narcissism. This moves every social actor to critically participate in activities that make the society habitable for its inhabitants across all borderlines, statuses, creeds and classes. *Esibi* performance is a domestication of social activism among the Akure people because the performance avails the performers the opportunity to speak the truth to powers without fear or let.

Demystifying Local Colour

In folkloric and cultural studies, certain features of performances, myths or print literature often emphasise and foreground the origin of such art form. These literary or aesthetical features are called local colours. Local colours are liminal, culture-specific or culture-based nuances with which a literary critic can trace the origin of the author or culture of origin of a work of arts. Local colour can be seen as the (re)presentation of the features and peculiarities of a particular locality, topography, its inhabitants as well as their cultural identity in writings especially literature. Chinweike Iwuchukwu (1998) extends the scope of local colours to the culture of origin of the performance and perceptive receptacle of the one studying them" (35). Abrams (1999) argues that "local colours cast a stress on the socio-cultural worldview and ideology of the people who own the performance" (150). Below are the liminal local colours deciphered from the purposively selected and critiqued *Esibi* texts as representative exemplifications of the local colours in general sense:

Local Colours in *Esibi* Performance

The local colours in *Esibi* performance are the masterfully and creatively crafted tapestries woven into its liminal fabric. The following aesthetical features and stylistic nuances help in the foregrounding of *Esibi* performance as an Akure oral poetry or indigenous performance:

Praise Poetry (Oriki of Akure Kingdom and some Families)

Oriki is one of the local and loric flavours in *Esibi* performance. Ajimisan (2012) argues that "oriki can better be described in the indigenous way as praise poetry instead of the use of concepts such as cognomen, eulogy or panegyric" (23) which reduce the form to just laudatory phrases or, loose words. This is in line with the assertion of Ola Ajimisan (2012). Ebiseni-Alfreds (2013) asserts

that Ekiki/Oriki is a "compilation of oral rendition in praise of a family, personality or nationality" (20). The oriki of the Deji of Akure or that of Akure as a sub-nationality of the Yoruba, and those of some prominent personalities and families in the metropolis feature interestingly in *Esibi* performance. Ajimisan (2021) features the Oriki of Akure in one of his poems "*The Birth of a Dawn*" in celebration of his Akure wife. Most of the lines in the poem were later rendered during one of the *Esibi* performances during the 10th Coronation Anniversary of the Deji of Akure Kingdom, Oba Aladelusi Ogunlade Aladetoyinbo, Odundun II. It goes thus:

Oba Aladetoyinbo, mo ya ki in King Aladetoyinbo, I have come to greet you

Ase Akure ma loo rin the authority of Akure is in your hands

Akure Olooyemekun. Akure, the land of the living leopards

Omokunrin Akure toko Ibo An Akure lad returns from the farm

O f'agada p'erin. He kills an elephant with a machete

Omobinrin Akure t'oja ibo An Akure lass returns from the market

O f'osinlo p'efon... And kills a buffalo with a dagger

Aba Oloye, mo ma rowo re. Our father the chief, I see your hands

Omo Oloja Oshodi Son of the head of Oshodi

K'en na koru. that is abuzz even till night

Oja Oshodi anoye... Oshodi market that ushers life

The text above is drawn from the live oral performance of *Esibi*. The *Esibi* text above features the praise poetry of Oba Aladetoyinbo, the reigning Deji of Akure Kingdom and that of Akure as a kingdom. It also features the praise poetry of Oshodi and those whose ascendancy is traced to the part of the present-day Akure situated adjacent of the Deji's Palace. See also, the text above for credence.

Historiography in *Esibi*

Esibi performance is also use for historiography, the modern art of writing and telling history among the people. Ebiseni-Alfreds (2012) sees historiography as "the writing or re-writing of history" (15). Ma-Cheng (2008) defines it as the "study of the history of historical writings" (236). Steven Knowlton views it as "dealing with the history of history" (256). Ajimisan (2021) is of the view that narratives and oral performances are tools of historiography (6). In one of the texts analysed below the lead performer revealed that Iralepo of Isinkan used to be under the authority of the Deji of Akure Kingdom and his territory was once a feudal settlement within the metropolitan Akure Kingdom until his stool was elevated to a kingship stool even through the consent and approval of the Deji of Akure. This is a reminder of the people's history that in the days when respect for constituted authority was the order of the day, Deji was the only prescribed authority over the vast territory that now covers Ifedore, Akure North and Akure South local government areas (now three local government areas) without controversy and disgruntled rivalry.

The text is provided below:

Ero Isinkan oro d'ola

Folks at Isinkan, the matter is bid for tomorrow

Iralepo oro d'ola

Iralepo the matter is bid for tomorrow

Oba o le pe meji laghofen. Two kings cannot rule a palace

Deji l'oba kete Akure. Deji is the king of the entire Akure

That part of the performance or rendition is a sad and brutal reminder of the past and pungent nostalgia on how such order and hierarchy had been disrupted, dismantled and depleted through incessant proliferation of lesser or vassal kingdoms from the larger or ancestral ones occasioned by chieftaincy commissions which hits us with the reality of the lesser one disrespectfully challenging the authority of ancestral monarchy and its occupant in modern age. Haven established significance of the performance in the teaching, re-teaching, telling, re-telling, writing, re-writing and re-thinking or re-perspectivisation of Akure history and tradition, it suffices to say that the performance is also a potent tool for ethno-nationalism. Ethno-nationalism is contextualised as ethnic nationalism, which connotes a systematic integration of entertainment and material ethics, cultural ethos for fostering and engendering patriotic zeal toward, and nostalgic bond with one's home soil. Like other indigenous, oral performances, *Esibi* is a child of necessity which engenders nationalistic values, cultural socialisation and renaissance. It reminds us of the dire need to take the propagation and transmission of our cultural heritage and identity with religious dedication to avoid cultural erosion or extinction. The text above lends credence.

Another pointer to historiography is the reference to Godwin Emefiele, the one-time governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria who hurriedly orchestrated the redesign of Nigerian currency notes and was also believed to have precipitated unwholesome and obnoxious policies to truncate the electoral victory of Asiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu who was a presidential candidate of a major political party in Nigeria. Pushed by the Fulani hegemonists and oligarchs who saw Bola Ahmed Tinubu as a threat if he became a president, Emefiele, without adequate preparation for the

transposition to cashless economy, declared the take-off of the policy. In the process, many people had money in their bank accounts but could not withdraw them because there was cash withdrawal limit both from the automated teller machine and from the counters. This escalated into the deaths of many people who had money in their bank accounts but had no access and the health facilities would not attend to them unless they made transactions in cash. The ill-thought-out policy also snowballed into economic policy summersault and sinister spike of inflation.

The Employment of Invectives in *Esibi* Performance

Lampoon, sarcasm and banter are integrated as invectives rendered to the accompaniment of the performance. Besides their performance during the festival, the Onisibis also perform in the streets in their local Akure dialect. One of most instructive kernels of the performance is the decisive and purposive interpolations of invectives into it for sermonic dialectics. *Sibi* performers sing by abusing people in their lyrics especially during traditional ceremonies (funerary rites, bridal rites, coronations, etc.) and they end up being paid for their services. They would sing to abuse people including the people of high status such as chiefs who sees it as fun and then give them money for their performances. The performers are led by a vocalist who sings in the Akure dialect and is backed by other members of the band. They perform using an object called ‘’apapara’’ which is a cow skin on a rod that looked like a hand fan. This is beaten with a stick as they perform. They could use simile in their abusive lyrical contents. They may say ‘you are as fat as a pig, dark as charcoal’ (odudu bi elede-egan, o ri demu-demu bi igba pito) to make others laugh to their jibes on whoever they are performing for as shown in the text above.

The Akure people, known to be wordy; the Onisibis are an epitome of their speech. The abusive tone of *Esibi* is not just for fun. It is for the purpose of moral re-engineering and value re-

orientation. Before the annual performance of *Esibi* that accompanies Aheregbe Festival, Ulefunta and other special communal events, lead performers of *Esibi* who are keen observers and social critics carefully observe and chronicle unfolding of events and use them to perform when the need arises. For instance, in the *Esibi* performance staged on August 12, 2025, the lead performer is heard saying:

Iralepo, oro d'ola	Iralepo, the scores will be settled tomorrow
Ase di meji n'ilu ria	Authority has now become duplicated in our town
Oba o le pe meji l'Akure.	Two kings cannot rule Akure at a time
Deji nukan l'apase Akure	Only the Deji is the constituted authority of Akure

The text above sees the lead performer of *Esibi* throwing banter and invectives at the Iralepo of Isinkan, a feudal settlement of Akure whose chieftaincy stool was recently upgraded to a monarchy but is now acting as a rival to his erstwhile lord, the Deji of Akure Kingdom. Before the Aheregbe Festival, Deji of Akure Kingdom, as has always been the practice, had announced that all markets and shops in Akure metropolis be closed, to avoid traditional sanction of having one's ware looted as is the long-standing tradition. The Iralepo was later heard saying that shops and markets in Isinkan can open for business since the authority of the Deji allegedly did not extend to Isinkan. The performer reminds the Iralepo of Isinkan that two captains cannot steer the wheel of Akure Kingdom since the only prescribed authority known by the people and the tradition is the Deji. He tells the Iralepo that he should wait for the outcome of the legal suit in which the Deji claimed that the Iralepo who is traditionally appointed by the consent and approval of the Deji stands suspended on the ground of insubordination.

In another text extracted from one of the performances, the lead performer threw banter and invectives at those who do drugs and alcoholism by deliberately mentioning Baba Asamo who is a complete gentleman and senior titled man in Akure Kingdom. In that wise, the invective was not for Baba Asamo or any of the elders there but for those who do drugs such as Colorado (colos), Canadian loud, cannabinoids and alcohol (Ogogoro):

Owelemu, Owelemu You always seek alcohol seller

Baba Deji omoluwabi Baba Deji is well-bred

Baba Asamo oni-kolos. Baba is a drug abuser

Alayapupo bi idin He is as polygamous as a maggot

The satirical import of the text is a deliberate criticism of the GenZ lifestyle which the author codifies as "GenZisation". GenZ lifestyle is a wayward and wild lifestyle, especially of the 21st-century teens and youths in which nothing matters and respect for elders, adherence to cultural mores and societal ethos are willfully denigrated or desecrated. The GenZ generation sees recourse to order or modesty dressing and moderation in lifestyle as old-fashioned and out of vogue. GenZ lifestyle, is therefore, a lifestyle which thrives on the unrepentant and sheer glorification of social rebelliousness and unfettered transgression against long-standing tradition and moral codes. To the GenZ generation, cyber-fraud and commodification of the female, now neatly packaged as hook-up or "olosho" are now ways to get rich quickly, albeit immoral. Social Activism Theory becomes effective and potent, not only for the purpose of checking the excesses of the leadership structures or their drivers but also for checking obnoxious, hydra-headed, juvenile delinquencies.

The stylistic and didactic significance of the invectives is to ridicule those who indulge in the social vices with a view to making them desist from the nefarious acts. One of the texts reads:

Iyale-ile, oro d'ola Promiscuous married women, we're talking to you

Oko di meji l'aya re husbands become two on your (who is in charge?)

Uwo sagbere, s'epe l'omo re by your promiscuity, you curse your children

Uwo gbera re kaakiri. you carry your body everywhere

Bi igba alate. like the tray of a roadside hawker

The invectives here are for those in the gathering either among the troupe members or the audience who are so promiscuous that they are married but are subtle sex workers, side-chicks and concubines to different men, who in Yoruba slang, are called "oloso" or "hook-up mamas". The coming of every performance is a call for moral sanity and sanctity. The fear of becoming the theme and subject-matter of next *Esibi* performance is not just the beginning of wisdom but also a nudge for moral re-adjustment. Thus, the invectives in *Esibi* performance are not just for fun but they are allegorically for didacticism and are full of pastoralist contents. Those who are abused are abused in order to expose them and make them retrace their steps.

The Use of Yoruba-morphic Costumes

During performances, performers and troupe members wear adornments produced purposely for the performance or otherwise. The adornments, most of which are clothing materials, are called costumes. Earlier, Omosule (2012) submits that "costumes are not only representational but also maintain duality with masks" (201). Enikuemehin (2012) is of the opinion that costumes may be

foreign fabrics or home-grown or home-knit Ofi or aso-oke (33). Omosule (2002) also sees costumes as being "anthropomorphic and zoomorphic from the peculiarity of each design" (393). Ajimisan (2022) maintains that costumes refer to the attires, clothing materials or adornments used or worn by the lead performer and members of his troupe (138). The "onisibis" are in full action during Aheregbe festival which has its origin in Oba-Ile (a part of Akure Kingdom). Members of *Esibi* troupe adorn themselves with the home-knit Ofi or aso-oke, Ankara, Guinea or other clothing materials sewn in indigenous styles and dance around the town for seven days as a form of rites to appease the gods for peace in the town. The "Onisibi" dancers which are either male or female are always half-dressed (females are seen in wrappers tied up to their chest level while the males only wear big skirts and are both adorned with coral beads and cowries). Some members of the troupe also attach strings of small-size metal gongs around their waists as both musical instruments and adornments. Thus, the gongs have double functions and essence in the performance. The rhythmic stamping of feet on the ground by the troupe members contributes to the musicality of the performance while the clustered gongs tied or woven to their waists and ankles also serve as parts of the costumes. Some of the troupe members also use palm-fronds to conceal or disguise their appearances and make them look clownish and funny. The palm fronds which form parts of their apparels also form parts of their costumes. Palm fronds also form parts of their symbolic transfiguration or emplacement into the spiritual realm or space of the ancestors and divinities.

The Use of Percussions and Musical Instruments in *Esibi* Performance

In most indigenous performances of African origin, drums and percussions are cardinal for overall synchronisation and symphony. *Esibi* performance is, in no way, different as it incorporates the employment of percussions into the performance. Ajimisan (2022) theorises that

Percussion instruments are basically musical instruments that are made to produce accompaniment sounds when hit with stick, hand or any other hard object. Some of them produce sound when they are shaken or rubbed against each other. African dance performances rely on the instrumentality of percussions to evoke robust and loud danceable rhythms (130).

The place of Afro-morphic and indigenous percussions and musical instruments are critical to the successful consummation of performances such as *Esibi*. John Kwabena Nketia (1963) buttresses this claim by submitting that "drums are made from local materials such as animal hides, hollowed woods; and are of different sizes, shapes with different sounds or tunes" (63). Without the agency of musical instruments and percussions, musicality or rhythm is not perfectly achievable. Owolola Ajulekun (2014) & (2018) posits that:

Drums are wonderful musical instruments and they have beautiful sounds. Drums are instruments that have the power of touching and awakening our souls and spirit whenever they are being beaten.

Instruments orchestrate indigenous values as well as the social and cultural direction of the people (45).

Esinlokun Olusanyin (1990) buttresses the position above on the significance of drums in rites and performances by submitting that "the technique of playing any drum is almost as relevant to the

kinetic response of the dancer (performer), as are the rhythms and dynamics" (160). Like other performances and rites, although there are not many drums and percussions used in *Esibi*, there is the use of Bembe drums, metal gongs held in the hands or tied around the waist like loins or girdles and "sekere" (beaded gourds). The metal gongs tied around the waist are smaller in size and they are in cluster so that as the troupe members wiggle their waists while dancing, the many metal gongs strung together like abacus or pieces of meat on barbecue sticks jingle against one another to produce sound.

Conclusion

This study has examined the various perceptible local colours that form the formative thresholds of *Esibi* performance among the folks of Akure Kingdom in the present Ondo State, Nigeria. The study shows how the local colours form the "walked" (lived) and "talked" (professed) creeds and existential liturgy of the folks. The study does eclectic documentation, perspectivisation and preservation of the social values, cultural norms and ethos of the people that cannot be documented at a glance or in one handy book. The performance is not only telepathic in its reach or richness but also encyclopaedic in contents. This study, therefore, recommends constant re-enactments and re-perspectivisation of the performance for the purpose of root preservation/retrieval, social consciousness, socio-spiritual cohesion and social re-engineering aided by the influx of the digital media.

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